

Discovery of Eliquis®/Apixaban, a Novel Factor Xa Anticoagulant and Chan-Lam Coupling Reaction

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Abstract:

Thrombosis is the leading cause of death in developed countries. There is a significant need for novel antithrombotics with an improved safety profile to replace Warfarin which has been in use for ~60 years and has significant bleeding issues. Factor Xa is at the junction of the intrinsic and extrinsic pathways of the coagulation cascade. Preclinical data has demonstrated that blocking FXa is an effective approach for anticoagulation with improved safety profile. Utilizing structure-based drug design tools, focused screening, and ADMET innovations, we at Bristol Myers Squibb had discovered a novel class of potent, selective and orally bioavailable Factor Xa inhibitors culminating in Eliquis®/Apixaban. Eliquis® was recently approved by FDA and named the “Best New Medicine of 2012” by Med Ad News. Eliquis® is currently a “block-buster” drug with annual sales of >\$5B. In 2015, the Eliquis discovery team received the American Chemical Society Heroes of Chemistry Award for a successful commercial product that benefits human well being.

During the optimization process, we have also discovered the powerful Chan-Lam Coupling reaction of copper promoted C-X bond cross-coupling via boronic acids, a complementary reaction to the Nobel prize Suzuki-Miyaura C-C bond Coupling reaction. In addition, at the molecular recognition frontier, we have pioneered the first rational use of halogen bonding in structure-based drug design.

Eliquis®/Apixaban

Keywords:

Factor Xa inhibitors, Eliquis®, apixaban, structure-based drug design, Chan-Lam reaction, halogen bonding.

References:

1. Discovery of 1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-7-oxo-6-(4-(2-oxopiperidin-1-yl)phenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-carboxamide (Apixaban, BMS-562247), a Highly Potent, Selective, Efficacious, and Orally Bioavailable Inhibitor of Blood Coagulation Factor Xa." Pinto, D. J. P.; Orwat, M. J.; Koch, S.; Rossi, K. A.; Alexander, R. S.; Smallwood, A.; Wong, P. C.; Rendina, A. R.; Luetzgen, J. M.; Knabb, R. M.; He, K.; Xin, B.; Wexler, R. R.; Lam, P. Y. S.. *J. Med. Chem.* 2007, 50, 5339-5356.
2. Copper-promoted Carbon-Heteroatom bond cross-coupling with boronic acids and derivatives. Qiao, J. X.; Lam, P. Y. S. *Syn.* 2011, 829-856.
3. Halogen bonding a world parallel to hydrogen-bonding Symposium in Organic Division, #58, ACS, August 16-20, 2009. Washington DC. Highlighted in *C&E News*, Sep 21, 2009, p39-42, "...to the best of our knowledge, this is the first successful use of halogen bonding in rational drug design..."

Biography:

Dr. Lam is a medicinal chemistry and drug discovery consultant. He currently collaborates with Blumberg scientists in terms of drug discovery and jointly supervises Blumberg chemistry postdocs and visiting scientists.

Dr. Lam has 30 years of extensive experience in innovation in structure-based drug design, ADME, focused libraries, molecular recognition and nucleic acid therapeutics to deliver biopharma clinical candidates with novel profiles. He is responsible for the discovery of a total of eight clinical candidates. At Bristol Myers Squibb, Dr. Lam was the group leader/co-inventor responsible for the discovery of Eliquis®/Apixaban, a novel Factor Xa anticoagulant recently launched on the market. Eliquis® is projected by analysts to be a transformational medicine with "block-buster" sales potential. Eliquis® was chosen as the "Best New Medicine of 2012" by *Med Ad News*. He and his team were awarded 2015 American Chemical Society Heroes of Chemistry Award for the discovery of Eliquis®. Dr. Lam is also the inventor of the novel cyclic urea class of HIV protease inhibitors that resulted in Mozenavir/DMP450. In Phase II clinical trial, Mozenavir was shown to be as efficacious as Merck's Crixivan, but without the lipodystrophy side effect of Crixivan.

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Expanding the Medicinal Chemistry Toolbox to Access New Chemical Space in Drug Discovery

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Abstract:

Identification of small molecule leads in drug discovery has been largely dependent on organic synthesis to deliver the designed ligands against target proteins. The expansion of synthetic methodology in recent years has greatly facilitated the preparation of molecules that would once have been considered an insurmountable synthetic challenge. In turn, the pharmaceutical industry, where large numbers of molecules are prepared and tested for their therapeutic use became the principal end-users and beneficiaries of this enlarged toolkit. Designing and discussing of various synthetic tools for the synthesis of medicinally important heterocycles and generation of new chemotypes with translational potential will form the basic premise of my presentation.

Keywords:

Synthetic methodology, chemotypes, drug discovery , toolkit, small molecule leads

References:

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Biography:

It is indeed a great pleasure for the Institute that Dr. Partha Sarathi Das has been chosen to receive the prestigious CRSI Bronze Medal for his incomparable research contribution in the field of Chemistry by Chemical Research Society of India (CRSI). CRSI was established in 1999 as part of the 50th Anniversary of the Country's Independence. The main objectives of the CRSI are to recognize, promote and foster talent in chemistry and chemical sciences and to improve the quality of chemical education at all levels. The CRSI organizes conferences, seminars, workshops, symposia and other related programmes to facilitate and promote research in all branches of chemistry. This medal will be conferred to him in the upcoming significant event of CRSI. His felicitation, definitely has brought laurels for IIT(ISM). Dr Das, having his Post-Doctoral degree and experiences from reputed institutions like Harvard University, USA, Tohoku University, Japan and RWTH-Aachen, Germany, started his career as Senior Scientist @ Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, Hyderabad. He has had more than 10 years of industry experience before joining as Senior Scientist at Integrative Medicine Centre of (CSIR) at Jammu. Currently, he is serving as Associate Professor in the Department of Applied Chemistry at IIT(ISM) Dhanbad since December, 2017.

His areas of expertise are –

- Catalysis and Heterocyclic Chemistry
- Medicinal Chemistry and Drug Discovery
- Total Synthesis of Biological Active Molecules
- Affordable Synthesis of FDA-Approved Drug
- Synthesis and Characterization of Drug Impurities

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Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Amide Derivatives of Pyridines as Anticancer Agents

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Abstract:

We have synthesized a series of amide derivatives of pyridine (10a-j) and its chemical structures were confirmed by ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and mass spectral data. Further, these compounds were tested for their preliminary anticancer activity against four different human cancer cell lines such as MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), DU-145 (prostate) and MDA MB-231 (breast) by MTT assay and etoposide used as standard drug. All these derivatives were exhibited well to moderate activity compare to standard drug. Among them, four compounds (10b, 10c, 10h and 10j) were showed more potent activity.

Cicletanine (1)

Crizotinib (2)

Keywords:

Pyridine, MCF-7 ,MTT assay , etoposide, anticancer activity

Acknowledgments:

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References:

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3. Siegel, R.; Naishadham, D.; Jemal, A. *CA Cancer J. Clin.* 2013, 63, 11-30.
4. Anand, P.; Kunnumakara, A.B. *Pharm.Res.*, 2008, 25, 2097–2116.

Biography:

Prof. Jayashree has 28 years of professional experience with active research and teaching commitments. Ph.D graduate from Osmania University in 1992 with UGC/CSIR NET fellowship. Fellow of professional bodies like Telangana Academy of Sciences, Indian Chemical Society (ICS), American Chemical Society (USA), The Indian Science Congress Association, Indian Council of Chemists, Indian Association of Chemistry Teachers (IACT, TIFR) etc. Teaching postgraduate students for the past 25 Years.

Research activities mainly include extraction, synthesis, molecular modeling and biological activity screening (invitro, invivo and exvivo) of medicinally important natural products. Currently supervising 10 full time research scholars working for Ph.D. Degree with CSIR/UGC/INSPIRE Research Fellow ships at Centre for Chemical Sciences and Technology, Institute of Science and Technology, JNTUH and 20 part time research scholars from reputed pharma industries are enriching the research group with their contribution. Published more than 160 research papers in national and international journals and conferences. Attended more than 75 National and International conferences and presented scientific papers in conferences including International conferences organized at USA, China, Dubai, Hyderabad etc. Organized various national and international conferences and seminars. Designed and organized 4 UGC sponsored Refresher Courses in chemistry (3 weeks) at academic staff college, JNTUH, for chemistry teachers. Delivered expert lectures in chemistry at JNTU Hyderabad, various P.G. centers of Osmania University. Receptient of meritorious BEST TEACHER award from state Government of Telangana 2016. Elected as Fellow of Telangana Academy of Sciences for the year of 2016. Recipient of Research Excellency Award-2015 from the Indus Global Foundation and Bharat Shiksha Ratan Award-2016 from Global Society for Health & Educational Growth. Biographical-Note is included Asia/Pacific Who's Who, Vol XV for 2016. Elected as Fellow of Royal Society of Chemistry UK in the year 2017

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Registration and Pharmacovigilance Requirements for Biosimilars in Singapore and Malaysia

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Abstract:

In the light of the expiration of a number of patents on first generation recombinant protein therapeutics, biosimilars have attracted a great deal of attention. The regulatory requirements for registration of biosimilars in Singapore and Malaysia will be discussed to bring out the differences, and similarities with other reference agencies' biosimilar guidelines. An overview of pre and post market pharmacovigilance reporting relating to biosimilars in these 2 countries will also be provided.

Biography :

Joelle has over 12 years' experience in regulatory affairs in Asia working with biotechnology companies and pharmaceutical companies. After completion of her pharmacy studies in Singapore and various hospital assignments, Joelle started her Regulatory Affairs career in the pharmaceutical industry and has assignments spanning regional specialty pharmaceutical companies, large global pharmaceutical companies and other global biotechnology companies. On some assignments, she has headed the regulatory affairs, pharmacovigilance and quality departments in the affiliate of these companies.

With these assignments, Joelle has acquired a vast and diverse experience in key therapeutic areas as well as pre-and post- marketing regulatory activities in various geographical areas in the Asian region. As Director of Pharma To Market – Asia, Joelle coordinates services to companies in the region including regulatory affairs strategy, dossier preparation and submission management as well as ongoing maintenance of marketed products.

Notes:

Clinical Pharmacology Studies for new chemical entities or biologics

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Abstract:

Clinical pharmacology studies are conducted to gain a fundamental understanding of the safety, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamic activity of a drug in man. It is often described as a bridging discipline between basic science and clinical development. Studies evaluate external and internal factors affecting drug PK and PD like product/formulation, administration route, organ dysfunction, diseases, concomitant medications, food. Information in the form of therapeutic index, and exposure-response and PKPD correlation studies support the design of Phase 3 clinical trials. Clinical pharmacology studies contribute covers important aspects supporting label claim, and patient information leaflet. This presentation gives outline for the studies conducted to characterize the Clinical Pharmacology of a drug and describe important design aspects of these studies.

Keywords:

Pharmacokinetics, Pharmacodynamics, organ dysfunction, clinical trials.

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